

THE ROLE OF THE BULELENG DISTRICT DEPARTMENT OF INDUSTRY, TRADE, COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN PROVIDING LEGAL PROTECTION OF THE INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS OF MSME ENTERPRISES IN BULELENG DISTRICT, BALI

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received May 05, 2024 Revised May 10, 2024 Accepted May 25, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Intellectual Property Rights, Legal Protection, MSME Business Actors</p>	<p>This research investigates the role of the Buleleng Regency Industrial Trade and SME Cooperative Service in providing legal protection for the intellectual property rights (IPR) of MSME industry players in Buleleng Regency, and the obstacles faced in these efforts. Using empirical legal methods and non-probability sampling, the study involves the Department of Trade, Industry and Cooperatives, and MSME business actors. Data collection techniques include document study, observation, and interviews, with qualitative descriptive analysis. The findings reveal that the Department's role encompasses preventive measures like intensive outreach, IPR registration recommendations, technical guidance, and collective IPR registration facilitation, as well as repressive measures such as providing legal assistance during IPR violations. Obstacles include low awareness and understanding of IPR among MSME actors, the complexity of the registration process, limited competence of some employees, and an annual quota for IPR registration recommendations.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">This is an open-access article under the CC-BY 4.0 license.</p>

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INTRODUCTION

National economic development must provide benefits to all Indonesian people, not just a handful of people, in accordance with the 1945 Constitution, especially Article 33 Paragraph (1). Therefore, the national economy must rely on family-based collaboration to achieve success. Legal protection for Indonesian MSMEs is one way to achieve this goal.

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are community-owned businesses that provide basic needs (Harsono, 2014: 14). The Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Law (UU No. 20 of 2008) details the classification of businesses as MSMEs. Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are generally owned by individuals or corporate entities known as business actors. Business actors make handicrafts, food, processed plants, etc. Hartini (2011:5) states that every MSME product has tangible and intangible value. That is why MSME products are protected. The Indonesian economy relies on the MSME sector. Based on research by the Ministry of Industry, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) contribute 60% of Indonesia's economic growth. This shows how important MSMEs are to the Indonesian economy. In the six years since 2016, MSMEs have absorbed 97.22% of Indonesia's workforce. MSMEs are very important for the Indonesian economy. MSMEs improve the local economy by empowering communities and opening new markets, as well as improving the balance of payments and providing employment opportunities (Saputra, Heniyatun, Hakim, & Praja, 2021). Apart from that, GDP shows the contribution of MSMEs to the Indonesian economy (Laily, 2016:2).

GDP is the value of all goods and services produced by a country in a certain year. The aim is to summarize financial transactions in certain monetary units over time (Indayani & Adelia, 2019: 122). The entire value of all MSME economic sectors contributes to national GDP. Based on data from the Ministry of Cooperatives and MSMEs, MSMEs have the potential to contribute IDR 8.573 trillion to national GDP in 2021 at current prices.

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) can drive people's economic activities and generate money, thereby increasing welfare. Therefore, the government must encourage fair commercial collaboration that benefits large and small businesses and increase human resources to empower MSMEs. This business organization shows how MSMEs can create jobs and distribute development results to advance the nation's economy. The Buleleng Regency Central Statistics Agency reported 57,216 MSMEs. MSMEs can employ 129,325 people in 2021.

The Buleleng Regency Department of Trade, Industry, Cooperatives and SMEs reported as many as 60,000 MSME units. Only 39 MSMEs have IPR. There is a need to protect the IPR of MSME players, both woven products, endek, and processed foods such as dodol Penglatan Buleleng Regency. MSMEs must prioritize intellectual property in their products. The government has helped MSMEs develop and compete, enabling them to innovate and produce new goods.

Intellectual property rights are intangible assets that can be owned like conventional property. Intellectual property rights are now part of our daily lives and corporate competition. Intellectual Property Rights (IP) is an important idea that led to these rights being included in the 1994 WTO Agreement. This Agreement covers all intellectual property rights, as do similar international agreements.

Trade in goods and services in Indonesia has grown rapidly due to developments in information technology and transportation infrastructure. Trade growth often correlates with economic growth. Economic and commercial operations depend on intellectual creations such as brands.

Indonesia uses a constitutive system that follows the concept of trademark registration which was first proposed based on Law Number 20 of 2016. Trademarks registered with the Directorate General of Intellectual Property Rights of the Ministry of

Law and Human Rights (DJKI) are automatically protected. . Due to the increasing emphasis on free trade, brands are very important in controlling corporate competition. In good condition. Brands need legal protection, especially for MSMEs. Because brands are very important nowadays, regulations that encourage MSMEs to register their products as brands are very important. MSMEs fail to enforce intellectual property rights for various reasons:

1. MSMEs often imitate the products of other companies that already have IPR, because this is clearly in conflict with TRIPs;
2. Lack of awareness and ability of MSME actors in efforts to register IPR;
3. Lack of innovation and product development

Rapid economic expansion and innovation in various company sectors, including MSME businesses, are their motivation to produce and market their products. Therefore, MSME players must create consumer confidence in their offerings.

MSMEs need global competitiveness to build an integrated market. This allows them to expand domestically and internationally. Therefore, MSMEs need support, opportunities and legal protection from the government. Strong MSME assistance is like supporting economic companies founded individually.

MSMEs face fewer opportunities. MSMEs lost their operations and activities because they were replaced by large corporate organizations. Effective corporate management, extensive market relationships, and vast financial resources help these large companies penetrate and dominate many markets and networks. These factors are what hinder start-ups such as MSMEs.

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) must register intellectual property rights because of the many benefits. Trademark or copyright registration protects the intellectual property of MSMEs. Therefore, micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) have exclusive rights to their goods or services and can sue anyone who uses or imitates them.

In addition, establishing intellectual property rights improves the brand image and commercial reputation of MSMEs. MSMEs can identify their products and create consumer trust by registering brands. This helps MSMEs maintain market share and build consumer relationships. MSMEs benefit from product rights registration. This increases the brand value and reach of the product. This increases the growth and sustainability of the company.

MSMEs make a significant contribution to the economy, although the government prioritizes larger businesses. Meanwhile, MSMEs function independently. This statement is contrary to Article 33 of the 1945 Constitution which requires the implementation of the economy to provide benefits to all Indonesian people. Large commercial entities benefit from the existing market system, which uses market procedures. MSMEs are increasingly excluded from the market. MSMEs do not have the same business opportunities, therefore the government must prioritize their safety and build a security framework based on economic justice.

The Buleleng Regency Trade, Industry, Cooperatives and SMEs Service carries out Regional Government functions related to decentralization, deconcentration and assistance to trade, industrial and SMEs cooperatives. These tasks are planned strategically to fulfill the vision and goals of the Buleleng Regency Government. The Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs develops and advances regional

MSMEs. This research examines intellectual property rights in Buleleng Regency MSMEs.

This study shows that Indonesian MSMEs face problems that are contrary to the constitutional goals of a people's economy. Even though the national goal is to improve people's welfare through a fair and comprehensive economy, MSMEs still find it difficult to realize their maximum potential, especially in protecting intellectual property rights. The report emphasizes the need for concrete action to close this gap, and suggests government agencies help MSMEs and protect them legally.

This research examines how well the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs protects the intellectual property rights of MSME business actors. This research aims to identify operational problems and provide authoritative recommendations and corrective actions for the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs to protect the intellectual property rights of MSMEs. industrial players who comply with IPR principles.

Based on the background description above and the lack of research on this issue, especially in the Buleleng area, the author proposes a research project entitled "The Role Of The Buleleng District Industrial, Trade, Cooperative And Sme Department In Providing Legal Protection Of The Intellectual Property Rights Of Umkm Business Activities In Buleleng District, Bali".

METHODS

This research uses empirical legal research. This empirical legal research method allows identification and analysis of policies, regulations and legal practices implemented by the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs regarding the legal protection of intellectual property rights for MSME business actors. This research uses descriptive research, which attempts to systematically describe and explain accurate facts that exist in a particular area. Data and sources Using primary data and secondary data. The legal material for this writing can be classified into three, namely primary legal material consisting of legislation, secondary material consisting of material obtained indirectly from theoretical studies in the form of legal opinions, teachings (doctrine) and legal theory as support obtained from books. - literature books, laws, regulations, scientific journals and the internet, tertiary legal materials in the form of research materials obtained from the Beisar Indonesian Dictionary, ensiklopeidia, and so on).

Data collection techniques in this writing consist of three, namely, document study techniques, observation and interviews. This research uses the Purposive Sampling method. Purposive sampling refers to the method of selecting or determining representatives based on certain criteria and attributes. Purposive sampling is a method used to select samples based on certain criteria or considerations (Sugiyono, 2016:85).

Data processing includes the process of tidying up data obtained from data collection in the field to facilitate analysis. This research data will be analyzed qualitatively, specifically focusing on non-numerical data obtained from observations, interviews and written materials.

According to Bogdan, data analysis in qualitative research is a process of carefully searching and collecting data from interviews, field notes and other materials to make it easier to understand and communicate the findings to others (Sugiyono, 2018:334). Qualitative data, also known as naturalistic data, consists of words that have not been processed and have not been converted into numerical values. The collection is through observation and interviews, and does not take the form of numerical data. The analysis process is carried out iteratively in the field and includes findings at the data collection stage, which are presented descriptively, qualitatively and systematically. By analyzing the data obtained, the data will be used to improve accuracy and address the problem being investigated

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

IPR Registration Mechanism in Buleleng Regency

The mechanism for registering IPRs in Buleleng Regency, which was obtained based on the results of interviews with the Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs, Buleleng Regency, is as follows.

1. Preparation Stages in Buleleng Regency
 - a. The Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs conducted outreach about the importance of IPR registration to MSME business actors. And counseling and seminars on *Picture IPR Registration Mechanism in Kab. Buleleng* IPR registration procedures.
 - b. MSME business actors can consult with the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs to obtain detailed information about the IPR registration process. The Department provides assistance services in preparing the required documents.
2. Submission Stage in Buleleng Regency
 - a. Administrative Document Collection
 1. Registration application form (available at the DJKI office or website).
 2. Applicant's identity (KTP/SIUP/TDP).
 3. Examples or descriptions of intellectual property rights to be registered.
 4. Power of attorney if authorized.
 5. Proof of payment of registration fees.
 - b. Initial Examination

The Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs carried out an initial inspection to ensure the completeness of the documents. If the documents are incomplete, the applicant is asked to complete them.

- c. Recommendation

Once the documents are declared complete, the department provides registration recommendations to the applicant. This recommendation is used to submit a registration application to the Balitbang BRIDA Buleleng Regency.

3. Registration Stage at National Level

a. Applicants submit an application for IPR registration online via the official DJKI website (<https://e-hakbuat.dgip.go.id>) or manually at the DJKI office. Attach all prepared documents and recommendations from the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs.

b. Formality Check

DJKI checks the completeness of documents and administrative requirements. If the documents are complete, DJKI will proceed to the substantive examination stage (for brands and patents).

c. Substantive Examination

DJKI examines the substance of registered intellectual property rights to ensure newness, originality and the absence of conflicts with registered IPRs.

d. Announcement

For trademark and patent registration, DJKI will announce the application in the Official Brand or Patent Gazette during a certain period to provide an opportunity for third parties to submit objections.

e. Certificate Issuance

If there are no objections or if the objection can be resolved, DJKI will issue the appropriate IPR certificate (brand, patent or copyright).

4. Certificate Retrieval Stage

Applicants can take the IPR certificate that has been issued at the DJKI office or the Buleleng Regency Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs Service. The Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs can help inform business actors about the registration status and certificate collection process.

The role of the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs in efforts to provide legal protection for IPRs of MSME industry players in Buleleng Regency.

Legal protection is an effort provided as a concrete manifestation of what is mandated by the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, article 1 paragraph (3), namely that Indonesia is a rule of law state. So the protection provided is a legal effort that must be given to the community in order to ensure that every community's rights are not harmed. Legal protection is something that must be considered regarding the losses experienced by victims and preventing repeat incidents. Legal protection is providing protection for human rights that are harmed by other people and this protection is given to the community so that they can enjoy all the rights granted by law (Satjipto, 2014: 77). Legal protection is the protection of honor and dignity, as well as recognition of human rights

possessed by legal subjects based on legal provisions or as a collection of regulations or rules that will be able to protect one thing from another (Philipus M. Hadjon, 1987:25) .

Legal protection as intended can be divided into two, namely preventive and repressive legal protection (Muchsin, 2003:14).

1. Preventive legal protection

This research found several roles in the Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs in Buleleng Regency in an effort to provide legal protection for the IPRs of MSME industrial actors in Buleleng Regency, which are included in the form of preventive legal protection efforts, namely: 1) Intensive guidance for the MSME actors regarding the importance of IPR 2) Provide recommendations for IPR registration to MSME actors 3) Provide technical guidance and assistance to MSMEs during the IPR registration process 4) Facilitate collective IPR registration for groups of MSME business actors.

1) Intensive coaching for MSME players regarding the importance of IPR.

Through coaching programs and activities, this agency seeks to increase awareness and understanding of business actors regarding the benefits and procedures for IPR registration. This training includes education about various types of IPR, such as copyrights, trademarks, patents and industrial designs, as well as the steps that need to be taken to obtain legal protection. In this way, MSME players can protect their work and innovation, increase competitiveness, and avoid the risk of legal violations that could harm their business. This development is in line with the theory of legal protection seen as a separate illustration of the function of the law itself, which has the concept that the law provides justice, order, certainty, benefit and peace. Legal protection is very necessary for humans in their behavior in society to distribute justice to society. In essence, legal protection is the protection of dignity and worth, and the recognition of human rights possessed by legal subjects in a legal state, originating from the conditions of arbitrariness (Philipus M. Hadjon, 1987:25).

2) Provide recommendations for IPR registration to MSMEs.

This recommendation is a form of official support that strengthens their application before the relevant authorities, in this case the Breda Research and Development Agency, Buleleng Regency. Through these recommendations, the agency ensures that MSMEs understand the importance of IPR in protecting their innovation and creations, as well as assisting them in fulfilling the administrative requirements needed to obtain valid legal protection.

3) Providing technical guidance and assistance to MSMEs during the IPR registration process.

The Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs is active in providing technical guidance and assistance to MSMEs during the IPR registration process. By providing the necessary information and consultation, this service helps business actors understand the complex and technical procedures related to IPR

registration. This assistance includes an explanation of the types of IPR that can be registered, such as copyright, patent and trademark, as well as how to submit an effective application.

4) Facilitate collective IPR registration for groups of MSME business actors.

The Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs plays an active role in facilitating collective IPR registration for groups of MSME business actors. By encouraging and assisting the registration of collective IPRs, this agency seeks to protect and preserve the cultural heritage and traditional knowledge of the Buleleng people. The Department provides assistance and outreach to business groups regarding the importance of collective IPRs, registration procedures, and the benefits that can be obtained from this protection. Some examples of MSMEs that already have collective IPRs in Buleleng district are the Dodol Training Center and the Center for Wood Weaving Craftsmen in Tigawasa Village. This is in line with government efforts through Law Number. 20 of 2016 concerning Marks and Geographical Indications provides collective brand protection. Sourced from the description of Law Number. 20 of 2016 concerning Marks and Geographical Indications, a collective mark is a mark used on goods and/or services with the same characteristics regarding the nature, general characteristics and quality of the goods or services as well as their supervision which will be traded by several people or legal entities jointly. the same to differentiate it from other similar objects and/or services.

2. Repressive legal protection

Repressive legal protection by the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs is realized through providing legal assistance to MSMEs when violations occur related to Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). In this case, the department plays an active role by providing legal consultation services, accompanying business actors in the litigation process, and collaborating with law enforcement agencies to ensure that the rights of MSME actors are protected and enforced in accordance with statutory regulations. This legal assistance includes providing competent lawyers or legal consultants to help MSME actors sue IPR violators, as well as carrying out advocacy to ensure that business actors receive fair compensation or compensation. This effort aims to provide a sense of security and legal certainty for MSMEs, so that they can continue to innovate and develop without fear of experiencing violations of intellectual property rights.

Obstacles that influence legal protection efforts in protecting IPRs of MSME business actors by the Buleleng Regency Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs Service.

Based on research conducted at the Buleleng Regency Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs Service, data has been presented regarding the role of the Buleleng Regency Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs Service in efforts to provide legal protection for the IPRs of MSME Industry players in Buleleng Regency. In efforts to legally protect

IPRs of MSME business actors, several obstacles were found that hampered the role of the Buleleng Regency Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs Department. The obstacles or things that influenced these efforts were:

- 1) Lack of legal awareness and ability of MSME business actors to protect intellectual property rights

According to Soerjono Soekanto, legal awareness involves understanding, recognizing and enforcing the law in various aspects. Legal awareness is important because it involves legal knowledge which then forms recognition and respect for legal rules. Apart from that, the law also needs to be followed so that it can be enforced.

According to Soerjono Soekanto, there are four indicators to assess legal awareness, namely 1) legal knowledge, 2) legal understanding, 3) legal attitudes, and 4) legal behavior patterns. Some MSMEs do not meet these indicators, including:

- 1) Some MSME business actors do not yet have adequate knowledge about IPR and the Trademark Law and Industrial Design Law.
- 2) Some MSME business actors do not understand the importance of protecting their product brands.
- 3) Some MSME business actors do not yet have a supportive legal stance, because implementation is considered complicated, which is a reason for not registering.

Many MSMEs do not realize that by protecting IPR, they can prevent unauthorized use of their work and products by other parties, as well as increase the added value and competitiveness of their business in the market. Apart from that, the lack of technical capability in accessing and understanding IPR registration procedures is also a significant obstacle. The registration process, which is often complicated and requires a special understanding of law and administration, can make MSMEs reluctant to involve themselves in IPR protection efforts.

- 2) Lack of understanding regarding the importance of Intellectual Property Rights, types of IPR and their benefits by MSME business actors,

The lack of understanding regarding the importance of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) by MSME business actors as well as the types of IPR and their benefits is a significant obstacle in legal protection efforts by the Buleleng Regency Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs Service. MSMEs often do not fully realize the strategic role played by IPR in protecting their innovation and creativity from misuse and imitation by other parties. This may be caused by a lack of access to adequate information regarding IPR and a lack of understanding of the business implications of IPR protection. Many MSMEs still view IPR protection as not very important or even consider it a burdensome bureaucracy. They tend to focus more on the production and marketing aspects of their products rather than involving themselves in the IPR registration process which is considered complicated and time consuming. This lack of understanding means that many

MSMEs do not make optimal use of the legal protection provided by IPR, thereby increasing the risk of theft and misuse of their work and products by other parties.

IPRs consist of various types, including copyrights, trademarks, patents, and industrial designs, each with different characteristics and registration procedures. However, many MSMEs do not understand the differences between these types of IPR and the benefits they get from appropriate IPR protection. This lack of knowledge means that many MSMEs are unable to utilize the legal protection available to protect their innovation and creativity effectively. They may not realize that by protecting IPR, they can prevent unauthorized use of their work and products by other parties, as well as increase the competitiveness and added value of their products in the market.

3) The complexity of the IPR registration process involves several institutions in the registration process and confusing registration information.

The IPR registration process, which includes copyrights, trademarks, patents and industrial designs, often requires collaboration with several related institutions such as the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs and then with the Buleleng Regency Research and Development Agency and the Ministry of Law and Human Rights Human (Kemenkumham). The involvement of several institutions makes the registration process complicated and time consuming. Apart from that, another obstacle is confusing registration information which often makes MSME players confused and have difficulty understanding the steps that must be taken in the registration process. Information regarding the administrative requirements, procedures and costs required for IPR registration is often inconsistent and difficult for MSMEs to access. This has resulted in many MSMEs feeling inhibited and reluctant to involve themselves in the IPR registration process, thereby increasing the risk of infringement and misuse of their intellectual property rights.

The complexity and complexity of the IPR registration process makes it difficult and lazy for many actors to manage their IPR. This is certainly not in line with the definition of bureaucracy as an organization consisting of clear rules and procedures, measurable separation of duties, and a strong hierarchy. Max Weber saw bureaucracy as a rational and efficient system in carrying out its duties. Therefore, improvements need to be made to overcome this, such as bureaucratic reform which aims to increase efficiency and quality in public services. And also by creating a one-stop service or one-stop integrated service to make managing IPR easier, without the hassle of having to visit from one institution to another.

The Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs faces a number of internal obstacles in carrying out its role in providing legal protection for Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) for MSME business actors in the region. One of the main obstacles is the lack of competence of some employees in providing IPR-related services to MSME business actors. This causes the process of providing information, consultation and assistance regarding IPRs to not run optimally, so that many business actors do not understand the importance of registering their intellectual property rights.

Apart from that, another obstacle is the limited quota for providing recommendations for IPR registration each year. This limited quota means that only a small number of business actors can obtain recommendations for IPR registration, resulting in many business actors having to wait a long time or not even get the opportunity to protect their intellectual property rights. These two obstacles are a big challenge for the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs in their efforts to provide adequate legal protection for MSME business actors.

These obstacles could be a weakness for the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs in providing legal protection for the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) of MSME business actors for several reasons. First, the lack of employee competence in providing services related to IPR means that MSME business actors do not receive accurate and complete information regarding the importance of registering their intellectual property rights. This can result in business actors not understanding the benefits of IPR protection, so that they are not encouraged to register. Apart from that, employees who are less competent may also be unable to provide adequate assistance in the registration process, making business actors experience difficulties in fulfilling the necessary administrative requirements.

Second, the limited quota for providing recommendations for IPR registration each year means that only a few business actors can enjoy this facility. Business actors who do not receive recommendations have to wait or even do not get the opportunity at all, which in the end can reduce their motivation to register intellectual property rights. This has the potential to weaken legal protection for MSME business actors, because without IPR registration, they are vulnerable to copyright, patent or trademark infringement by other parties.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and the discussions that the researchers have carried out, several things can be concluded as follows:

1. This research reveals that the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs has a role in providing legal protection for the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) of MSME business actors. This department carries out various programs and activities to increase awareness and understanding of business actors about the importance of IPR. These efforts include intensive guidance regarding types of IPR such as copyrights, trademarks, patents and industrial designs, as well as providing recommendations, technical guidance and assistance during the IPR registration process. Apart from that, the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs also facilitates collective IPR registration for MSME business groups and provides legal aid services if violations related to IPR occur.
2. This research also found several obstacles that hamper efforts to legally protect IPRs by the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs. Obstacles identified include a lack of awareness and understanding of MSME business actors about the importance of IPR, low knowledge about the types of IPR

and their benefits, as well as a complicated IPR registration process that involves several institutions and is often accompanied by confusing information. Many MSMEs feel burdened by complex registration procedures and lack of access to clear and consistent information. And the obstacle found internally at the Buleleng Regency Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and SMEs was the lack of competence of several employees in providing IPR-related services to MSME business actors. And there is a limited quota for providing recommendations for IPR registration each year.

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